

A Study on Socio Economic Status of Parents of Intellectually Disabled Children of Minority Owned Special Institutes

Vaheeda Kayikkara

Research Scholar, Mahatma Gandhi University,
Kottayam, Kerala, India

ABSTRACT

Birth of a new child in a family is a time for rejoicing and celebration in a family. Parents have so many dreams and aspirations for their newly born child that birth of a child with intellectual disability can be a traumatic and shattering event for a family. The feeling of grief and loss that the family goes through is caused by realization that the anticipated normal child they had waited for nine months was never born. There is much evidence that family members experience a range of emotions in response to a diagnosis of intellectual disability including denial, shock, anger, grief, guilt, embarrassment, depression, withdrawal, ambivalence and fear of stigma. The information collected from the study will throw light to the life of intellectually disabled children as well as to the parents of the children. The data was collected from 10 minorities owned institution for intellectually disabled children and from parents of 77 intellectually disabled children.

Findings reveal that By analyzing information collected from parents of students who studies in the institutes it was found that socio economic statues of parents of children with intellectual disability have significant bearing on the statues of their disability. And it also contends that despite the national level awareness towards the disability, especially intellectually disabled, still a major section of our population is affected by such problem due to lack of information, awareness and necessary social support system in place. If we want to see our future generation free from such diseases, we need to have a clear roadmap and honest intention to execute such strategies. Only then the dream of a better future can be realized by our next generation. The parents with

low level of educational and economical back ground tend to have more children with such disability because of certain degree of awareness missing from their decision making pattern in their lives.

Keywords: *intellectually disabled children, special educational institutes*